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Influence of Digital Finance Platforms on Financial Inclusion in Mombasa County, Kenya

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Abstract:

Financial inclusion involves increasing the number of individuals that have access to formal financial services mainly through having formal bank accounts, which contributes to poverty reduction and economic growth. An inclusive financial system is desirable and will provide opportunities for all people, particularly the poor, to access and move funds, grow capital, and reduce risk. The study sought to determine the influence of digital financing platforms on financial inclusion in Mombasa County. Theories anchoring this study include Financial Intermediation Theory, Finance growth theory and Informational asymmetric. The research population for this study was regional managers of the commercial banks in Kenya, which are licensed and regulated by the Central bank of Kenya. Data collection instruments included questionnaires. In this research the questionnaire were accompanied by a list of anticipant's answers where the respondents selected the best answerers that described the situation. The said questionnaires were administered directly to responsible officers. The data presentation was done using the both descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. They include the mean, standard deviation, percentages and tables. Multiple regression analysis was used to establish the influence of digital finance on financial inclusion in Mombasa County, Kenya. The study results shows a strong positive correlation coefficient of 0.761 between digital financing platform and digital financial inclusion which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that Board and management of commercial banks in Mombasa County, Kenya should digitalize their banks and provide proper, appropriate and timely direction in financing their commercial banks through digitalization to enable them improve on their overall financial inclusion for effective and efficient financial service delivery to customers. Management and leadership of commercial banks Mombasa County should emphasis more on the digital finance aspects that had the highest mean such as "Online brokerage has influence on financial inclusion in my organization" in order to achieve and improve on their financial inclusion. Further research studies can build on the findings of this study to broaden the existing knowledge on the influence of digital finance on financial inclusion of commercial banks in Mombasa County, Kenya.

Keywords: Digital Finance, Financial Inclusion

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Financial inclusion is the practice of providing underserved populations, such as women and low-income individuals, with inexpensive access to financial services and credit when they need it (Chen & Divanbeigi, 2019). Access to financial services and goods such bank accounts, insurance, remittance and payment services, and financial consulting services is referred to as financial inclusion. It enables people to make plans for their financial security in the future; a sizable bank account offers a reliable deposit basis in addition to chances to invest, save, and borrow money (Evans, 2018). Nearly 85% of recent advances in digital platforms have originated from the digital banking sector, demonstrating that access to banking is improving in emerging nations (Van Der Boor, 2017). Globally, the percentage of adults who had a bank account or used a mobile money service increased from 51% in 2011 to 69% in 2021 (Ferrata, 2022). The onset of a global epidemic has intensified this tendency of cashless purchases. Evidence suggests that the COVID19 emergency has increased digital payments in particular, which has aided in accelerating digital financial inclusion, (Global Findex, 2021). A 2016 report by the McKinsey Global Institute estimated that digital finance alone could boost the annual GDP of all emerging economies by \$3.7 trillion by 2025 due to productivity gains of businesses and governments.

In China, home consumption practises including online shopping and digital payments have hastened the growth of financial inclusions (Li, Wu, & Xiao, 2020). With the help of public policy and legislation, digital platforms (digital financing, investment, money, and payment) have dramatically increased financial inclusion (Hua and Huang, 2020). Mobile money platforms, which made use of telecommunications networks to provide low-cost payments and other financial services by phone to numerous customers, played a particularly important role in boosting access in Sub-Saharan Africa. In order to reach their consumers, traditional financial institutions and a developing ecosystem of Fintech platforms employ mobile money networks throughout Africa (CCAF, 2020). Since the baseline Survey in 2006, when access to formal financial services and products was 26.7 percent, there has been an increase in Kenya's overall access to these services and products. Since then, formal access has increased from 82.9 percent in 2019 to 83.7 percent in 2021. This expansion is the result of advancements in financial technology, particularly in mobile banking and mobile money.

Financial inclusion is regarded as a crucial strategy for lowering destitution and advancing a nation's broad financial improvement, according to (Baccklay & Malady, 2015). Money-related consideration fosters overall development as more flexible and transparent budgetary administrations promote growth and reduce poverty and imbalances. According to (Bhrat, 2014), budgetary consideration supports the idea that improvements in financial transactions lead to improvements in the economy as a whole. The incorporation of money also starts with a large-scale perspective, which gives it a direct relationship between the integration of money in a given country and its prosperity and wellbeing as measured by its Gross domestic product. However Measuring the number of people who own and utilize formal financial instruments is a common way to assess financial inclusion (Klapper, El-Zoghbi, & Hess, 2016). The usage of digital platforms has been quickly adopted by most institutions and is essential for every organization's system of smooth operation. Digital platforms offer a variety of components to help businesses operate more effectively as a universal coverage. Depending on the applications, these components have a range of textures and uses. As a result, they include, among other organizational pillars, finance, marketing, and sales. Digital finance is significant in this study and is currently a potent method for gaining access to financial services for various sectors, including agriculture and transportation among many others.

The term "digital finance" refers to a wide range of new financial goods, financial business operations, financial-related software, and novel financial services offered by internet service providers, according to (Gomber & Koch, 2017). From the perspective of practitioners, digital finance is the delivery of financial services via internet and mobile services that are connected to a secure digital payment system. In a similar

vein, (White & Berry, 2016) define digital finance as financial services supplied via mobile phones and the internet cards in their Mckinsey Report. While there is no agreed-upon definition of digital finance, there is general agreement that it refers to all goods, services, technologies, and infrastructure that allow people and businesses to access payments, savings, and credit facilities online without having to physically visit a bank or without dealing directly with the financial service provider.

Financial services made available through digital platforms are intended to support emerging nations' goals of financial inclusion and poverty reduction (United Nations Report, 2016). Any digital financial service should have three essential elements: a digital transactional platform, retail agents, and a device utilized by consumers and agents, most frequently a cell phone. (CGAP, 2016). To use the digital financial services (DFS), a user must already have a bank account in their name, as well as the finances necessary to send or receive money in cash via digital platforms including personal computers, mobile devices, or the internet.

The CGAP defines digital financial inclusion as the population who are excluded and less fortunate using formal financial services online (CGAP, 2015). Currently, novel digital financial services have been introduced via mobile phones and similar devices in at least 80 countries to persuade millions of underprivileged consumers to use digital financial services entirely as opposed to cash-based transactions (GSMA, 2014). In order to carry out fundamental financial transactions remotely, the excluded and less fortunate population must have access to the internet. This assumption underlies the entire process of achieving digital financial inclusion. A successful digital financial inclusion program should be developed to meet the needs of the excluded population if the excluded and less fortunate groups can be convinced of the benefits of digital financial inclusion. This needs to be given in a responsible manner at a price that is reasonable for both customers and suppliers.

The Governor of the Central Bank of Malaysia (2016) noted that a string of technological advances combined with the widespread use of mobile devices presented a significant opportunity to scale up financial inclusion to previously unheard-of levels in his opening remarks at the global symposium on innovative financial inclusion. He added that practically every financial sector activity has been affected by financial innovation, which accelerated problem-solving and computing speeds and raised the level of financial inclusion. According to Boko, 2017, there is a significant link between financial inclusion and mobile banking in Kenya.

According to Kenya's Vision 2030, the growth of the financial sector is a crucial driver of the achievement of general macroeconomic goals and objectives. As a result, a comprehensive financial system has been acknowledged as a crucial policy factor for Kenyan counties. Kenya has taken action in the last ten years to strengthen banking sector confidence and broaden the country's financial inclusion. The Kenyan government has a policy in place to ensure accessible financial services, particularly for the most disadvantaged members of society hence enabling simple access to and reasonable usage of financial services. As a result, the entire Kenyan society is exposed to the idea of financial inclusiveness.

How many people use formal financial instruments is sometimes measured in financial inclusion (Hess, 2016) It also refers to the formal financial system's inexpensive financial product and service provision, particularly to excluded members of an economy (Thorat, 2007). The lack of a sizable number of adults in the working age range in the formal financial sector, however, calls into question the idea of financial inclusion in digital finance operations.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It is pleasant Digital finance platforms provide an effective way to increase access to financial services beyond those typically provided manually to other economic sectors including agriculture, transportation, health, and education, among others. This feature of DFS was represented by how user-friendly and streamlined the

interface is. The adoption of such communication tools as mobile phones, smart cards, telephone banking, internet banking, Mpesa transactions, and agency banking makes this clearly visible (Kariuki, 2005). As things stand, the reach of DFS and its growth are highly dependent on inclusion, particularly in the area of finance. Global financial inclusion, which embodies the holistic notion of participation as a policy, enables greater and better sustainable economic and social growth.

Due in part to urban societal exposure and dependable digital infrastructure, the level of financial inclusion in the past was solely restricted to the wealthy metropolitan population. As a result, only a small number of important commercial centers and towns, like Nairobi, Mombasa, Kisumu, and Nakuru, were better positioned on the financial platforms. Even in these towns and cities, not every resident was using the financial platforms and benefiting from financial inclusion. The few wealthy and affluent members of these organizations nevertheless had exclusive access to the scope and bracket operations in these cities and towns. According to a deductive approach based on the aforementioned fundamental setup, the great majority of Kenyans living in small commercial towns and rural locations were excluded from the idea of financial inclusion because they lacked dependable digital access.

However, thanks to recent developments in recent years, the Kenyan government has made significant strides toward achieving financial inclusion on the digital platform by creating an environment that makes it possible for such platforms to function, such as expanding internet connectivity, increasing the country's electrical coverage, etc. Many platforms are running right now and doing well. This covers programs like mpesa, tala, orach, etc. Despite this increase, a sizable portion of Kenyans who have access to both formal and informal financial systems and are financially capable are not included in the digital financial platforms. This shows that, contrary to popular opinion, many portions of the population have not been impacted by digital banking and financial inclusion. Which means that, there is a discrepancy between the financial resources available, their accessibility, and their use or transactional on a digital banking platform to promote financial inclusion. Thus, the researcher's concern about why sizeable percentages of Kenyans—nearly 50%—have not been included in digital banking platforms to improve its financial inclusivity—is captured.

1.3 Objective of the study

The objective of the study was to determine the influence of digital financing on financial inclusion in Mombasa County, Kenya

1.4 Research question

The research sought to answer the following questions:

- i. What is the influence of digital financing on financial inclusion in Mombasa County?

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical framework

The assumption that a sizable portion of the excluded population owns (or has) a mobile phone and that the delivery of financial services via mobile phones and related devices can increase access to finance for the excluded population forms the theoretical basis for the relationship between digital finance and financial inclusion (Worldbank, 2014) Greater availability of digital finance is frequently predicted to have favorable effects for financial inclusion, all other things being equal; implying a positive correlation between the use of digital finance and access to formal financial services. This is assuming that the excluded population has a mobile phone and reasonably priced internet connectivity positive correlation between the use of digital finance and access to formal financial services.

2.2 Financial Inclusion Theory

Financial inclusion, according to Ozili (2018), is the provision of financial services to all members of the population, particularly the poor and other excluded groups, as well as their access to those services. Financial inclusion can also be referred to as offering banking services to the vast majority of disadvantaged and low-income groups at a reasonable cost (Dev, 2006). Other definitions of financial inclusion, according to Sahay et al. (2015), include having access to and using formal financial services. All of these definitions place a strong emphasis on the requirement that all members of society have access to the available financial services.

Determinants of financial inclusion

Understanding the elements affecting financial inclusion is crucial for developing policy. There is, however, a lot less research in this area than there is in studies on financial development. Of course, there is a positive correlation between financial inclusion and development. Improvements in financial development will purportedly benefit the less included segments of society as well, but this is not a given, just as there is a big difference between growth and inclusive growth. It would only have an inadvertent effect if the objective was not to improve the financial situation of the less advantaged rather than the average.

According to an important study by Beck et al. (2007), the positive impact of financial development on income is demonstrated to be larger in the lower segments of the income distribution than on average. Despite the fact that this shows the positive consequences of general financial development, it does not prove that financial inclusion will necessarily follow. Although lower financial inclusion is unquestionably associated with lower income groups, these two characteristics are distinct.

Supply side factors

The researcher investigates the forces influencing financial development in this essay while acknowledging the possibility that it may have a negligibly good impact on financial inclusion. Private credit, which refers to loans from the financial industry to private borrowers (while purposefully excluding loans to the public sector for political reasons), is the most important indicator of financial progress. Several actions can be made to enhance personal credit. In essence, there must be a system for distributing credit as well as the autonomy to choose who to lend to and under what conditions. In order to guarantee the validity and enforcement of loan agreements, a framework is also required. Although it is anticipated that these factors will also boost financial inclusion, there hasn't been a lot of systematic empirical research in this field, and inclusion and development are not the same thing (Beck et al., 2007). Beck et al. (2008) analyse price and non-price obstacles to access and consumption of banking services in developing countries using survey data from 209 institutions in 62 countries. They find that these barriers have a negative impact on measures of financial inclusion or capital access. It has been shown that annual fees, minimum checking account balance requirements, and the documentation requirements for opening an account are all extremely restrictive barriers. The study also sought to examine the interactions between these barriers and the legal systems of the various countries. They discovered strong correlations between several measures of bank restrictions, bank disclosure policies, and media freedom. As a result, Beck et al. (2009) provided a lengthy list of actions that may be taken to increase access to finance for a significant portion of the population. Building credit information systems, according to them, can help developing countries have access to money, especially credit. Similar to this, access may be easily improved with the aid of procedures for collecting debt from contracts. Promoting openness and competitiveness can make it easier to reach previously underserved portions of the population (Barajas et al., 2020). However, there is more contradictory data about direct state intervention. Government payments should be made through bank accounts, according to the precise advice given by Barajas et al. (2020). The most extensive paper analysing supply-side components of financial inclusion was written by Allen et al. (2016). They use the first iteration of the Findex database from 2011 and 123 countries with roughly 1,000 randomly chosen survey respondents each

(dropping about 20 countries due to missing information). They use these data to show links between various supply-side traits and financial inclusion. The latter is evaluated based on account ownership, savings over the past twelve months, and at least three withdrawals from any account during a typical month, among other factors. Supply-side determinants are available at the federal level. There are three categories of characteristics that are strongly connected with financial inclusion after taking individual attributes into account: (i) Financial inclusion and lower financial service costs, such as those associated with opening a bank account or obtaining direct credit, are positively correlated; (ii) financial inclusion is associated with better physical infrastructure, such as bank and ATM penetration; and (iii) financial inclusion is associated with a more reliable politico-economic environment. On the other hand, other variables like deposit insurance, the degree of consumer protection, and the government's or foreign banks' ownership of financial institutions have little to no bearing on financial inclusion (Allen et al., 2016). One method to perhaps lower the still high level of financial exclusion is to use contemporary financial technology, notably mobile money (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018). The idea is that almost everyone, especially in developing countries, owns a mobile phone, even if it is not necessarily a smart phone, and that these phones can be used to implement financial services. Undoubtedly, there have been triumphs in this area. Mobile money, which was first introduced in Kenya less than 15 years ago, now has hundreds of millions of users. For the first time, many of them are using formal financial services (Suri, 2017). Financial inclusion has increased dramatically as a result. The greatest research has been done on money transfers in the event of negative shocks, despite the fact that using mobile money has several benefits (Aron, 2018). But there are limitations. More than 40% of mobile money account holders in a case study in rural Uganda by Hamdan et al. (2020) show the large gap between account holders and mobile money users. The owners of mobile money accounts also have access to new populations, although women, the elderly, and those who are typically less well-off continue to be underserved. Additionally, there are still gaps in mobile money's accessibility, particularly in remote areas that are generally underdeveloped. Not to mention, many consumers seem to struggle with understanding fees, which may help to explain why their need for financial services is based on "misinterpreted" rates. Financial technology clearly has a role to play in the problem of financial inclusion, but it also has the potential to leave out sizable segments of the population.

2.3 Digital financing

Banks have always provided financial resources to both people and businesses. Venture capital, angel investing, and government financing programs are a few more sources of funding for businesses and start-ups (Klöhn and Hornuf 2012). By leveraging the Internet to obtain the required money, digital financing enables individuals, businesses, and start-ups to become independent from these conventional methods. All digital methods of distributing capital are included in digital financing. Today, a number of platforms provide digital services in the fields of crowdfunding, factoring, invoicing, and leasing. It is important to distinguish between the terms "Digital Finance" and "Digital Financing." While the latter is a general word encompassing all company tasks, including financing, the former exclusively concentrates on financial elements. A sort of supplier financing known as factoring occurs when businesses sell their creditworthy accounts receivable at a discount (often equal to interest + service costs) in exchange for quick cash (Klapper 2006). The original creditor typically sells a full portfolio of receivables from a variety of clients to a "factor." A diverse portfolio like this one will diversify the creditor's risk from each debtor. Reverse factoring entails a lender "purchasing receivables solely from particular informationally transparent, high-quality buyers" (Klapper 2006). Here, the factoring procedure is started by a supplier's customer. Reverse factoring enables suppliers to receive financial support so they can supply goods or services to customers. Electronic factoring via online platforms has facilitated the initiation of such factoring relationships tremendously.

Getting clients to pay their open accounts is another way for businesses to obtain financial resources. In order to communicate invoice data electronically in an organized and standardized manner that enables automated processing, electronic invoicing offers quick, easy, and dependable services (Penttinen, Virpi, & Tuunainen,

2011). The time it takes to pay the bills is shortened with greater overviews, faster transmission, and account settlement.

When people or businesses lack the cash on hand to purchase assets like automobiles, trucks, or machinery, leasing can help. While the asset is still in the lessor's hands, the user can use it right away. Nowadays, there are many service options online for leasing financing. Electronic leasing has thus emerged as a convenient way for people and businesses to acquire the required assets without having to pay the full cost up front.

The word "crowdfunding" refers to a burgeoning area of digital financing that encompasses a variety of financing options. Crowdfunding, according to Belleflamme et al. (2014), "involves an open call, conducted primarily online, for the provision of financial resources, either in the form of a donation or in exchange for a future good or other type of reward to support initiatives for specific reasons." Special project websites are developed on crowdfunding platforms to showcase the campaign and receive support from the online community, or "crowd." Thus, unlike traditional finance, a large number of people who support an initiative by making relatively small contributions are addressed rather than a single intermediary or a small group of experienced investors. The fundamental concept of financing through numerous little donations is not new, but the Internet has cut transaction costs, sped up transaction times, and made it simpler to connect those in need of money with those in a position to lend it (Zhang and Liu 2012). Because incredible huge sums of money can be raised when numerous people support an endeavor, crowdfunding is highly effective.

2.4 Financial inclusion

Empirically, there is a wealth of work that explains how financial inclusion and economic growth are related. According to several studies, there is a favorable association (Chatterjee, 2020). For the years 2004 to 2012, Inoue and Hamori (2016) examined the impact of financial access on economic growth in 37 sub-Saharan African nations. The study used the panel dynamic GMM estimator, and the findings revealed a link between real GDP per capita and the quantity of commercial bank branches. Additionally, financial deepening had a favorable and considerable impact on sub-Saharan Africa's economic expansion. Additionally, from 2007 to 2015, Thomas et al. (2017) looked into the connection between financial accessibility and economic growth in eight South Asian nations. The results of using the GMM estimators demonstrated that rising financial accessibility resulted in rising income. Furthermore, economic growth in low-income nations was more affected by rising financial access indices than it was in middle-income countries. In a similar vein, Kim et al. (2017) used dynamic panel estimation, panel vector autoregressive (VAR) methodology, impulse-response functions (IRFs), and panel Granger causality tests to examine the association between financial inclusion and economic growth in 55 Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) countries. Dynamic panel estimations' findings demonstrated that financial inclusion has a beneficial impact on economic growth. Malinda and Maya (2018) used a pooled regression model, a vector error correction model, and Granger causality tests to investigate the relationships between financial inclusion and economic growth in 11 countries from 2007 to 2016. The results showed a long-term connection between financial inclusion and economic expansion. In addition, Sethi and Acharya (2018) used the following panel data models: country-fixed effect, random effect, and time fixed effect regressions, panel cointegration, and panel causality tests to examine the effect of financial inclusion on economic growth for 31 developed and developing countries from 2004 to 2010. The findings showed a long-term, positive association between financial inclusion and economic growth throughout the studied nations, as well as a causal relationship in both directions between financial inclusion and economic growth and economic growth. The study found that financial inclusion had an impact on economic growth and suggested that, over time, policies that promote financial inclusion will lead to better rates of economic growth. Inoue and Hamori (2019) used a panel of 168 nations between 2004 and 2014 to analyze the role of financial inclusion in the economic growth of emerging countries. The study examined the impact of increased access to formal financial services on financial inclusion and economic growth and discovered a link between real per capita GDP and the quantity of commercial bank branches. Additionally, financial deepening significantly and favorably impacted the countries' economies' growth. Similar to this, Makina and Walle (2019) used the system GMM dynamic panel data estimator to assess the impact of financial inclusion on economic growth in 42 African nations from

2004 to 2014. Financial inclusion has a positive and statistically significant impact on economic growth in Africa, according to research that measured it using the number of commercial bank branches per 100,000 adults. Van and Linh (2019) looked at how financial inclusion affected economic growth in 23 Asian nations between 2010 and 2015. The findings demonstrated a connection between a rise in economic development with the presence of numerous bank branches, ATMs, and domestic private sector lending. Similar to this, Siddik et al. (2019) examined the impact of financial permeation on economic growth in 24 Asian nations between 2004 and 2016. The study found that financial penetration significantly boosts the economies of Asian nations using Granger causality and fixed effect regression approaches. Additionally, the Granger causality test indicates that in Asian economies, there is a bidirectional causal relationship between economic growth and financial penetration. More specifically, Chatterjee (2020) looked at how ICT and financial inclusion affect economic growth. The study employed a fixed-effect model using data from 41 nations between 2004 and 2015; the findings showed the importance of financial inclusion in driving country growth in a dynamic panel data model, which is fueled by greater ICT penetration. The findings revealed that financial inclusion, both on its own and in combination with internet and mobile phone, can enhance per capita economic growth. ICT metrics do not significantly contribute to financial inclusion or economic growth in underdeveloped nations, nevertheless. In all eight SAARC (South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation) nations, Singh and Stakic (2020) looked studied the relationship between the financial inclusion index and economic growth from 2004 to 2017. The Pedroni panel co-integration test, Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square (FMOLS), and Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) methodologies were all used in the study. Financial inclusion and economic growth in the SAARC countries have a long-term association, according to the Pedroni panel co-integration test. The financial inclusion index and a few chosen control factors boost economic growth, according to the FMOLS and DOLS coefficients. The Granger causality test also supported the existence of a bi-directional causal relationship between financial inclusion and economic growth. Ain et al. (2020) used GMM to examine the connection between financial inclusion and economic growth for 33 developing nations between 2004 and 2016. According to the study, financial inclusion has a favorable effect on economic growth. Similar to this, Huang et al. (2021) compared the old and new EU (27) nations between 1995 and 2015 to assess the relationship between financial inclusion and economic progress. The study revealed that financial inclusion is crucial for economic growth and employed FMOLS and panel autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models to support its findings. In contrast to high-income and established EU countries, it is more significant for low-income and new EU countries. Additionally, Dahiya and Kumar (2020) examined the connection between financial inclusion and economic growth in the developing Indian economy from 2005 to 2017. Only the utilization component of financial inclusion has a relationship with economic growth, according to the study's estimation of the association using Bayesian auto regression. For the years 2014 and 2017, Nizam et al. (2020) looked into the impact of financial inclusion on economic growth in 63 developed and developing nations. The study made use of a cross-sectional threshold regression method and a fresh formulation of the financial inclusion indicator. They found a non-monotonic positive relationship between financial inclusion and economic growth that becomes more significant at higher financial inclusion index levels.

2.9 Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a diagrammatical depiction that shows how autonomous and ward variables relate to one another. For the purposes of this study, digital financial services include finance, investing, money, and payments, while credit penetration served as a proxy for financial inclusion. Theoretically, whereas the Technology Acceptance Model postulates that acceptance of digital financial services promotes accessibility of financial services by various users, the Theory of Financial Innovations suggests that implementation of digital financial innovations enhance financial inclusion. Numerous empirical studies demonstrate that financial innovations in the digital realm have an impact on banking organizations' operations in addition to improving customers' access to financial services even in the absence of traditional banking infrastructure. Figure 2.1 displays the conceptual framework of the investigation as follows.

Figure 2.1 Conceptual framework

3.1 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.2. Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design. The establishment of exact measurements and the reporting of features of some populations of phenomena are supported by descriptive research, according to Mugenda & Mugenda (2013). With special reference to Mombasa County, this design enables the researcher to get quantifiable data from the sample population and respond to questions about the current situation. This information used to assess the impact of digital finance on financial inclusion. According to (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009), descriptive research is frequently employed as the next stage of exploratory research, which aims to clarify and investigate an idea, event, or poorly understood phenomenon, or to propose hypotheses for additional research. According to Sekaran & Bougie, (2011), descriptive investigations create paradigms that, through qualitative or quantitative data, present a more comprehensive theoretical picture. In order to ensure that questions pertaining to the topic of study are answered, the approach incorporated the locations of data collection. The study was suitable since it demonstrated a causal connection between the variables and provides clear findings on the independent and dependent variables. Consequently, describing the link between financial inclusion and digital finance.

3.3 Target Population

The collective group of people in the study is referred to as the population. Population is defined by Mugenda (2008) as the total set of individuals, objects, items, cases, articles, or things that have similar qualities or traits. Population in research refers to the set of components among which a research issue is present. 39 regional managers of the 39 commercial banks in Kenya that are licensed and regulated by the Central bank of Kenya made up the research population for this study. Therefore, there was a 39 respondents overall (39). These regional managers are in crucial positions where the data needed for this study can be easily sought out and acquired. They are the personnel who have relevant information suitable to achieve the objectives of this research study.

3.4 Sampling frame and design

Sampling design, according to Mugenda & Mugenda, 2013, is the process by which a researcher chooses a specific sample from a population. The purpose of the sampling design was to methodically explain how the study sample was selected. All the study components that are available to the researcher when conducting a research study are said to be included in the sampling frame. It is made up of a collection of details that are typically used to determine a sample population for statistical analysis in a study. These details include a

numerical identification for each person, their traits, and a more in-depth analysis (Marshall & Rossman, 2014). It includes a list of everyone in the population who can be sampled, which could include people, homes, groups, or institutions. The sampling frame for the study will comprise all the 39 operation managers.

3.5 Sampling Technique

Using a sampling strategy, researchers select a collection of objects, people, behaviors, or sets that have certain traits. After taking samples from a target population in a way that serves to establish the population's hypothesis when the study reaches statistical insignificance, sampling strategy must use a specified model (Dang & Pheng, 2015). To include all 39 of Kenya's commercial banks' operating managers, a census sample technique was used since the population was small and was manageable.

3.6 Sample Size

A sample is a representation of components, individuals, or things taken from a specific target population with desired and unique characteristics for the study (Bryman & Bell, 2015). The statistical requirements for having a degree of precision that gives the range in the value of the genuine population being estimated must be taken into account while determining the proper sample size. The ability to draw reliable inferences about the research and population characteristics is the primary goal of sample size selection. The 39 operating managers of the commercial banks in Kenya were all included in the study, which employed the census sampling technique, thus the sample size won't need to be determined.

3.7 Data collection tools/ instruments

The researcher requested the relevant department for a letter of introduction, which was used to ask the National Council for Science, Technology, and Innovation for permission to do research (NACOSTI). The researcher proceeded to the appropriate divisions after stopping by the Mombasa County Commissioner's office for additional certification. At each location, the researcher left copies of the research permission and alert the Divisional officer that was intended to perform the study there. The research then headed to the field to get the required information.

Questions were used as data gathering tools. In this study, the questionnaires were followed by a list of potential respondents' responses, from which the participants chose the best ones to best explain the circumstance. Direct administration of the aforementioned surveys to accountable personnel within the aforementioned targeted institutions is planned. These officers were given a suitable amount of time to complete the surveys so that a more trustworthy response may be gotten from them. It was important to remember that all of the comments were only to be utilized for academic purposes, with absolute commitment to client confidentiality.

3.8 Data analysis and presentation

The investigation is anticipated to produce numerical data. Quantitative data are represented by numbers, but qualitative data are expressed by words (or other textual data), and these words are frequently categorized (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). A descriptive statistical technique was used for the data display. The mean, standard deviation, percentages, and tables are among them. Through the values that have been summarized, they made it much easier to interpret the data.

3.9 Ethical issues

In terms of secrecy, ethical considerations were followed to respect the participant's rights. Sharing study-related information with anyone who isn't involved in the study would be unethical on the part of the researcher. This was required to keep an eye on the study's and the researcher's integrity (Cooper & Schindler, 2003). The respondents were taken as conventionally informed, and the research only used their opinions.

4.1 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.2 Response rate

The total numbers of respondents who successfully completed the questionnaires and returned were received 33 out of a target population of 39 respondents. This represented 85% response rate which was considered good for analysis as stated by Mugenda and Mugenda (2012). Based on this outcome therefore, it implies that the response rate for this study was adequate and increases confidence for generalization and it formed the basis of the analysis and the results contained in this chapter.

4.3 Influence of digital finance platforms on financial inclusion

The assessment of the influence of digital financing platforms, digital investment platforms, digital money platforms and digital payment in Mombasa County in Kenya was done using descriptive statistics presented in Table 4.3 and 4.4 as variables.

4.3.1 Digital financing platforms

To assess the influence of digital financing platform on financial inclusion of commercial banks, the respondents were requested to respond on three attributes of commercial banks they represented. Table 4.3 presents these analyzed results of data from the respondents pertaining the extent of digital financing platform on financial inclusion of commercial banks in Mombasa County in Kenya.

Table 4.3: Digital financing platforms

Digital financing platforms	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Electronic factoring has influence on financial inclusion in my organization	33	3.99	1.14
Electronic invoicing has influence on financial inclusion in my organization	33	4.15	0.83
Electronic leasing has influence on financial inclusion in my organization	33	3.98	0.94
Average	33	4.02	0.97

From these results majority of the respondents agreed that there was an extent of digital financing platform on financial inclusion of commercial banks in in Mombasa County in Kenya. These results correspond with the results of a study conducted separately by Zhang and Liu (2012) who found that the fundamental concept of financing through numerous little donations is not new, but the Internet has cut transaction costs, sped up transaction times, and made it simpler to connect those in need of money with those in a position to lend it.

Moreover, “Electronic invoicing has influence on financial inclusion in my organization” is the attribute of digital financing platform that received the highest mean ($M=4.15$, $SD=0.83$). This meant that management of these commercial banks emphasized more on electronic invoicing compared to other attributes of digital financing platform such as “Electronic leasing has influence on financial inclusion in my organization” which got the least mean ($M=3.98$, $SD=0.94$).

This outcome concurs with that of Abubakar (2020), who investigated how automated teller machines (ATMs) affect user satisfaction in Nigeria. The study was conducted at United Bank for Africa in the Sokoto metropolitan area. An across-sectional survey approach was used to conduct the research, asking participants about ATM services. The majority of the study's participants were United Bank for Africa clients in the city of Sokoto. One hundred respondents who use ATM services made up the study's sample. Multiple logistic regression analysis was used for the examination of the gathered data. The results showed that ATM services have a favourable and significant impact on perceived ease of use, transaction cost, and service security. However, the result also indicates that the impact of ATM services in terms of availability of money is positive but insignificant.

4.4 Influence of digital finance on financial inclusion in Mombasa County, Kenya.

After the analysis of descriptive statistics of data on the variables were completed successful, correlation analysis was carried out to test the influence of digital finance on financial inclusion in Mombasa County, Kenya.

4.4.1 Bivariate correlation results

Table 4.5 present bivariate correlation results between digital finance variables (digital financing platforms) and financial inclusion in commercial banks in Mombasa County, Kenya. The results in Table 4.5 shows a strong positive correlation coefficient of 0.682 between digital financing platform and digital financial inclusion which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This means that on overall, digital financing platform is positively related to financial inclusion in commercial banks in Mombasa County, Kenya.

Table 4.5 Bivariate correlation results

Pearson Correlation		Financial Inclusion	Digital financing
Financial Inclusion	Pearson Correlation	1	.682**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	33	33
Digital financing	Pearson Correlation	.682**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	33	33

5.1 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.2 Conclusion

This study was guided by four objectives and after data analysis it is concluded that digital financing platforms, digital investment platforms, digital money platforms and digital payment platforms have a significant influence on the financial inclusion in Mombasa County, Kenya.

Digital financing platform

The results shows a strong positive correlation coefficient of 0.682 between digital financing platform and digital financial inclusion which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This means that on overall, digital financing platform is positively related to financial inclusion in commercial banks in Mombasa County, Kenya. Digital financing platform has the second influence on the financial inclusion in Mombasa County, Kenya compared to other independent variables such as digital investment platforms, digital money platforms and digital payment platforms.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that Board and management of commercial banks in Mombasa County, Kenya should digitalize their banks and provide proper, appropriate and timely direction in financing their commercial banks through digitalization to enable them improve on their overall financial inclusion for effective and efficient financial service delivery to customers. Management and leadership of commercial banks Mombasa County should emphasis more on the digital finance aspects that had the highest mean such as “Online brokerage has influence on financial inclusion in my organization” in order to achieve and improve on their financial inclusion.

5.4 Suggestions for further research

Further research studies can build on the findings of this study to broaden the existing knowledge on the influence of digital finance on financial inclusion of commercial banks in Mombasa County, Kenya. This study was limited to commercial banks in Mombasa County, Kenya that are regulated by Central bank of Kenya (CBK). Further research can therefore be conducted in other Counties within the coast region namely Kwale, Kilifi, Tana-River among others. Further research can also be carried out in commercial banks in all Counties in Kenya to cover other aspect of digital finance other than the ones involved in this study.

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